

Prediction of power through a wake-foil interaction model for oscillating foil arrays

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This research investigates and proposes a model for the wake-foil interactions between two oscillating foils in a tandem configuration. Oscillating foils can extract hydrokinetic energy from freestream flows through a combination of periodic heave and pitch motions at relatively high amplitudes and low reduced frequencies. For its highest efficiency modes, a strong leading-edge vortex (LEV) develops at the leading edge on the suction side of the foil and augments the lift with its low pressure core during maximum heave velocity. This benefit is short-lived as the vortex pinches off and convects downstream, similar to a dynamic stall cycle, but leaves behind a structured and periodic wake of vortices. Understanding the LEV formation and dynamics and the resulting wake structure is critical towards understanding and modeling arrays of oscillating foils. Even a system of two oscillating foils has up to 9 free parameters in terms of kinematics, spatial arrangement, and phase variables. This motivates the necessity of a reduced-order model for energy harvesting prediction of oscillating foil arrays, since brute force simulations are computationally intractable for such a large parameter space.

This work utilizes simulations of two tandem foils to parameterize and model the energy harvesting performance as a function of array configuration and foil kinematics. First, detailed simulations of a single oscillating foil are performed. This provides performance data on the baseline, or clean flow conditions. It also provides the model with time-resolved wake structures, from which data is extracted on the unsteady vortex timing, placement and strength. Next, a second foil is placed in the wake, and the developed model estimates how the power curve is modified from the baseline case due to 1) steady effects, or a reduction in the steady flow available, and 2) unsteady effects, or interactions with the large-scale vortices present in the wake. The model can predict the time-dependent power of the second foil as it changes its placement, phase angle, and kinematic stroke, from which an array efficiency can be obtained.

Results of the model are directly compared with fully resolved two-foil simulations, showing strong agreement for the tandem configuration. The proposed prediction model eliminates the need for costly simulations exploring the wide configuration and kinematic parameter space for an array of two oscillating foils, relying only on a database of highly resolved single foil simulations.